

ABOUT METHODS OF LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Annotation: At present stage of development of science, technology, international trade, different types of business communication a good command of foreign languages is not only a necessity, but also the need for specialists. There are many traditional methods of teaching foreign languages which are quite effective. However, the current development of society requires finding and using more advanced techniques and technologies.

Keywords: training methods, foreign languages, learning.

INTRODUCTION

In modern society, the role of foreign languages is increasing. Knowledge of a foreign language gives young people the opportunity to join the world culture, use the potential of the vast resources of the global Internet in their activities, and also work with information and communication technologies and multimedia teaching aids. Currently, intensive methods of teaching foreign languages are becoming more and more popular. There are many varieties of the intensive method, mainly used for teaching a foreign language to adults. However, at school, experienced teachers successfully use the techniques work inherent in this method.¹

While teaching students foreign languages the most effective methods are: a multimedia presentation, method of projects, interactive testing programs on-line (eg, TOEFL), on-line modules, interactive whiteboards, multimedia programs, the creation of a student's ELP, the "case" method (based on situational teaching methods), competency analysis (provides an assessment of game participants competencies, building professional diagram by specialty), distance learning, and others.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

These advanced techniques allow to achieve the following objectives: 1) the readiness to perceive educational material; 2) systematization of knowledge; 3) development of creative abilities of students; 4) self -education; 5) removing psychological barrier (fear to communicate, to make a mistake); 6) the comprehension of educational material, the analysis of the acquired material. One of the modern methods of teaching foreign languages is the use of computer

¹ Near peer role models. Teacher Talking to Teacher. 4 (3), 21-23. Mynard J. & Almarzouqi I., 2006.

technologies. Computer language programs add variety to the learning process, fostering a creative atmosphere and, at the same time, modify the learning process and facilitate the ongoing monitoring. One of the important points in learning a foreign language is a stage of reflection. Using a computer, students have the opportunity to analyze the results of their activities. The multimedia program «Learn to speak English», London language course "Air" (for intermediate and advanced levels), electronic encyclopedias «Encarta», Encyclopedia» have been of particular interest to students. Multimedia programs have a number of advantages:²

- 1) the use of exciting videos about countries with the text support, which can be removed by setting a task of high difficulty;
- 2) virtual voice contact with native speakers, the opportunity for the student to become a participant in the events and monitor the quality of foreign language communication;
- 3) the opportunity to learn to make an audio recording of his own speech and assess it through a correct pronunciation scale;
- 4) the opportunity to not only hear, but also see the speakers, to imitate their gestures and articulation;
- 5) the ability to merge the grammatical material with the use of games.

As English serves the purpose of international communication, most of the foreign language learners try to learn it. In this process, they have to acquire all the four basic skills of the language, viz. listening, speaking, reading and writing. Listening and reading are passive skills or receptive skills, whereas, speaking and writing are active skills or productive skills.

Fig: The Basic Language Skills of English

² Maslova A.M. «Essential English for Medical Students». M., 1981.

Speaking skill is the most important skill to acquire foreign or second language learning. Among the four key language skills, speaking is deemed to be the most important skill in learning a foreign or second language. Brown and Yuke (1983) say, "Speaking is the skill that the students will be judged upon most in real life situations".

Over the past decades, the methodology of teaching a foreign language has been developing under the sign of communication-oriented learning. The foreign language program for secondary school proclaimed as the main communicative goals, which set a certain movement for the learning process in this direction. The qualitative originality of the intensive method lies in the fact that in it these postulates are translated into real deeds; as a result, an integral and effective technology of intensive training has emerged, within the framework of which adequate communication mechanisms have been developed.

The features of this technology are as follows:

- 1) in the use of techniques that activate conscious and subconscious processes of the psyche to create an extensive and solid language base;
- 2) in the development of tasks that motivate communication;
- 3) in the optimal organization of the collective interaction of students with each other and with the teacher.

Method of projects is one of the most effective ways of organizing students' self-study, which is used in the final stage of the lesson's topic, i.e. as a consolidation or in the process of repetition. Project-based learning allows you to personalize the learning process, enables students to plan, implement and monitor their activities. Using the "project" method students can choose their own sources of information and forms of material presentation to show completely their creativity. Project work involves several steps. In the first stage the content and nature of the project, the sources and ways of finding information are discussed, individual tasks are distributed, or tasks for mini groups. Groups are formed according to the level of proficiency, psychological features and creativity. The second step is working directly with the project, such as collecting, summarizing and analyzing information; information exchange; compilation of vocabulary; writing a personal project; creating slides, drawings, posters and so on. n. The third stage is a presentation of the project. During the presentation, students demonstrate their fluency in a foreign language, demonstrate both prepared and spontaneous speech, especially

during the discussion after the presentation of the project. The work on the project will definitely increase the interest in learning foreign languages. Motivation helps students strengthen their cognitive and communicative skills. It is well known that a role-play is a means of simulation of problem situations in various spheres of human activity and it allows you to find the best solutions to many problems. A role-play is a comprehensive methodological procedure of learning in which students first consider the decision-making process. The role-play is a process of imitation in the model as a result of which there are some results and their consequences. The role-play is aimed at developing the students' skills to analyze concrete practical situation and make decisions.

RESULTS

The technique of working with Internet resources arouse a great interest and show effective results:

1. "Hotlist" is a list of Internet resources on the topic.
2. "Multimedia Scrapbook" is the study of multimedia reference collection (photos, maps, history, facts, audio, video fragments), selection of the necessary resources and the creation of the multimedia materials' collection.
3. "The Treasure Hunt" is a search for information to answer questions of specific nature of the subject under study; the existence of problematic issues on the content of sites and the final task are presumed.
4. Through "Subject Sampler" students explore the collection of selected references by a teacher, including questions based on the content of sites, and express their attitude; it is more complex activity than the "treasure hunt" having a student-centered character.
5. "Web Quest" is a project that uses a selection of Internet sites as the beginning of a comprehensive activities surveying different points of view on solution of the problem, group cooperation and the final draft by choice, sometimes integrating a role-play.

Thus, the use of a variety of advanced methods of teaching foreign languages has a number of advantages that help teach students to actively acquire a profound knowledge, develop their creativity and organizational skills and provide a powerful intention to learn the language. Advanced technologies enable perfectly combine theory with practice, form the content knowledge, skills and abilities.

References

1. Maslova A.M. «Essential English for Medical Students». M., 1981.

2. Khodjaeva L.U. Textbook "English", Tashkent, 2005.
3. Peer teaching: A description and evaluation. Teaching Sociology, 2(2), 133-146. Murphey. T. Australia, 1996.
4. Near peer role models. Teacher Talking to Teacher. 4 (3), 21-23. Mynard J. & Almarzouqi I., 2006.

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